

Neutrinos as a Window into New Physics?

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Outline

Non-Unitarity (NU)

- **Relation among flavor neutrino states and neutrino mass eigenstates is given by Non Unitary matrix.** The following relation among neutrino fields holds:

$$\nu_\alpha = N_{\alpha i} \nu_i$$

- Thus *CC and NC neutrino interactions are modified*

$$\mathcal{L} \supset -\frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} \left(W_\mu^- \bar{\ell}_\alpha \gamma_\mu P_L N_{\alpha i} \nu_i + \text{h.c.} \right) - \frac{g}{2 \cos \theta_W} Z_\mu \bar{\nu}_i \gamma^\mu P_L (N^\dagger N)_{ij} \nu_j$$

- This is **generated adding only this d=6 effective operator** to the SM

$$\delta \mathcal{L}^{\text{d}=6} = \frac{4\eta_{\alpha\beta}}{v^2} \left(\bar{L}_\alpha \tilde{H} \right) i \vec{\partial} \left(\tilde{H}^\dagger L_\beta \right)$$

Non-Unitarity (NU)

- *Several theories accounting for neutrino masses generate NU.* Typically extensions involving heavy fermions as type-I and type-III seesaws, some extra-dimensional constructions or Left-Right symmetric models.
- However, **when the SM is extended exclusively with fermionic singlets all the new physics effects are encoded in a NU leptonic mixing matrix.**
- Other extensions as type-III seesaw induce additional new physics effects leading to a more constrained scenario.

See for instance Biggio, Fernandez-Martinez, Filaci, J. Hernandez-Garcia, JLP 1911.11790

Minimal model: Mass Matrix

$$M_\nu = \begin{pmatrix} \overline{\nu^c} & \overline{N} \\ 0 & Y^T v / \sqrt{2} \\ Y v / \sqrt{2} & M \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \nu \\ N^c \end{pmatrix}$$

Light
Neutrino
Masses

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{v^2}{2} Y^T M^{-1} Y & 0 \\ 0 & M \end{pmatrix}$$

Minkowski 77; Gell-Mann, Ramond, Slansky 79
Yanagida 79; Mohapatra, Senjanovic 80

Mixing

Non unitary PMNS matrix

- Constraints from *EW and CLFV precision data*

Antusch, Biggio, Fernandez-Martinez, Gavela, JLP 2006
 Blenow, Fernandez-Martinez, Hernandez-Garcia, Marcano,
 Naredo-Tuero, JLP 2306.01040

"Direct" Searches

- Sterile neutrino oscillations, kinks in beta decays & peak searches in semileptonic meson decays, beam-dump experiments, colliders...*

The New Physics (NP) Scale

*kinks in beta decays
peak searches in semileptonic*

beam-dump experiments

colliders

*EW & CLFV
precision data*

Are
Neutrino Oscillation experiments
sensitive to
Non Unitarity effects?

Neutrino Oscillations vs NP scale

Kinematically
accessible sterile
neutrinos

Non-Unitary
mixing
(sterile states
integrated out)

Both limits can be studied
in a
unified & model independent fashion

$$U = \begin{pmatrix} \textcircled{N} & \textcircled{\Theta} \\ R & S \end{pmatrix}$$

$N_i - \nu_\alpha$ mixing

Deviation from unitarity of the PMNS matrix

General Parameterizations

- Triangular parameterization

$$N = (I - T)U$$

Deviation from unitarity

$$T = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{ee} & 0 & 0 \\ \alpha_{\mu e} & \alpha_{\mu\mu} & 0 \\ \alpha_{\tau e} & \alpha_{\tau\mu} & \alpha_{\tau\tau} \end{pmatrix}$$

Unitary matrix
(standard unitary PMNS
matrix
up to small corrections)

① Non-Unitary Mixing

Non-Unitary
mixing
(sterile states
integrated out)

① Non-Unitary Mixing

- What is measured in neutrino oscillation experiments

$$\tilde{P}_{\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\beta}(L) = \frac{\frac{dR_{\alpha \rightarrow \beta}}{dE}}{\mathcal{N}_{\text{tgt}} \epsilon \phi_\alpha \frac{d\sigma_\beta}{dE}} = \frac{\left| \sum_i N_{\alpha i}^* e^{-im_i^2 L/2E} N_{\beta i} \right|^2}{\sum_i |N_{\alpha i}|^2 \sum_j |N_{\beta j}|^2}$$

- When $NN^\dagger = I$ Standard three family probability recovered

Far Detector vs Near detector

$$\frac{dR_{\alpha \rightarrow \beta}}{dE} \sim \frac{\Phi_{\alpha}(E)}{L^2} P_{\alpha\beta}(L/E) \frac{d\sigma_{\beta}}{dE} \epsilon_{\beta}(E)$$

- **Sources of systematics**

- Cross sections
- Neutrino flux

- ***Near detector measurements reduce far detector systematic uncertainties***

- **New Physics at near detector (strongly affected by systematic uncertainties)**

Far Detector using ND data

- What is measured in neutrino oscillation experiments

Event rate
Far Detector

$$\tilde{P}_{\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\beta}(L) = \frac{R_\beta}{R_\alpha} = \frac{\left| \sum_i N_{\alpha i}^* e^{-im_i^2 L/2E} N_{\beta i} \right|^2}{\sum_i |N_{\alpha i}|^2 \sum_j |N_{\alpha j}|^2}$$

Extrapolation of Near Detector: flux and cross section are from measurements of same flavor at ND

Near Detector

- What is measured at Near Detector

$$\tilde{P}_{\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\beta}(0) = |\alpha_{\alpha\beta}|^2$$

zero
distance
effect!

Matter effects

- Effective potential in the mass basis

$$H_{\text{mat}, \oplus}^m = \sqrt{2} G_F n_e U^t \begin{pmatrix} 1 - \alpha_{ee} - \alpha_{\mu\mu} & \alpha_{\mu e}/2 & \alpha_{\tau e}/2 \\ \alpha_{\mu e}^*/2 & 0 & \alpha_{\tau\mu}/2 \\ \alpha_{\tau e}^*/2 & \alpha_{\tau\mu}^*/2 & \alpha_{\tau\tau} - \alpha_{\mu\mu} \end{pmatrix} U^*$$

- But Fermi constant also include NU corrections

$$G_F \simeq G_\mu (1 + \alpha_{ee} + \alpha_{\mu\mu})$$

Matter effects

- Effective potential in the mass basis

$$H_{\text{mat},\oplus}^m = \sqrt{2}G_\mu n_e U^t \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \alpha_{\mu e}/2 & \alpha_{\tau e}/2 \\ \alpha_{\mu e}^*/2 & 0 & \alpha_{\tau\mu}/2 \\ \alpha_{\tau e}^*/2 & \alpha_{\tau\mu}^*/2 & \alpha_{\tau\tau} - \alpha_{\mu\mu} \end{pmatrix} U^*$$

Aloni, Dery 2211.09638

- But Fermi constant also includes NU corrections

$$G_F \simeq G_\mu (1 + \alpha_{ee} + \alpha_{\mu\mu})$$

② Kinematically accessible sterile ν

Kinematically
accessible sterile
neutrinos

② Kinematically accessible sterile ν

1. The light-heavy oscillations averaged out at the near and far detectors.
Identical to NU case at leading order

Blennow, Coloma, Fernandez-Martinez, Hernandez-Garcia, JLP 1609.08637

2. The oscillation frequency dictated by the light-heavy frequency matches the near detector distance.

Oscillations could be observed at the near detector

See for instance talk by Mark Ross-Lonergan

sterile Neutrinos: 3+1

- What is measured at Near Detector

$$\tilde{P}_{\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\beta} = 4|U_{\alpha 4}|^2 |U_{\beta 4}|^2 \sin^2 \frac{\Delta m_{41}^2 L}{4E}$$

$$\tilde{P}_{\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\alpha} = 1 - 4|U_{\alpha 4}|^2 \sin^2 \frac{\Delta m_{41}^2 L}{4E}$$

Averaged-out regime

- What is measured at Near Detector

$$\Delta m_{41}^2 \gtrsim 100 \text{ eV}^2$$

$$\left\langle \tilde{P}_{\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\beta} \right\rangle = 2|U_{\alpha 4}|^2 |U_{\beta 4}|^2$$

zero
distance
effect!

$$\left\langle \tilde{P}_{\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\alpha} \right\rangle = 1 - 2|U_{\alpha 4}|^2$$

Averaged-out regime

- What is measured at Near Detector

$$\Delta m_{41}^2 \gtrsim 100 \text{ eV}^2$$

$$\left\langle \tilde{P}_{\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\beta} \right\rangle = 2|\alpha_{\alpha\beta}|^2$$

zero
distance
effect!

$$\left\langle \tilde{P}_{\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\alpha} \right\rangle = 1 - 4|\alpha_{\alpha\alpha}|$$

Low Scale
Non-Unitarity

② Kinematically accessible sterile ν

1. The light-heavy oscillations averaged out at the near detector.
Identical to NU case at leading order

Low Scale
Non-Unitarity

Present Bounds

90% CL
α_{ee}
$\alpha_{\mu\mu}$
$\alpha_{\tau\tau}$
$ \alpha_{\mu e} $
$ \alpha_{\tau e} $
$ \alpha_{\tau\mu} $

EW & CLFV
precision
data

Flavour & EWPO $m > M_Z$	
Direct	Schwarz
1.2×10^{-3}	$\alpha_{\alpha\beta} \leq 2\sqrt{\alpha_{\alpha\alpha}\alpha_{\beta\beta}}$
8.6×10^{-5}	-
6.0×10^{-4}	-
1.9×10^{-5}	5.4×10^{-4}
6.2×10^{-3}	1.5×10^{-3}
6.9×10^{-3}	1.5×10^{-4}

Blennow, Fernandez-Martinez, Hernandez-Garcia,
JLP, Marcano, Naredo-Tuero 2306.01040
Blennow, Fernandez-Martinez, Hernandez-Garcia,
JLP, Marcano, Naredo-Tuero, Urrea 2502.19480

Present Bounds

90% CL	Averaged ν Oscillations $m > 10$ eV		Flavour & EWPO $m > M_Z$	
	Direct	Schwarz	Direct	Schwarz
α_{ee}	8.4×10^{-3} Solar	-	1.2×10^{-3}	-
$\alpha_{\mu\mu}$	1.2×10^{-2} MINOS+	-	8.6×10^{-5}	-
$\alpha_{\tau\tau}$	2.9×10^{-2} IceCUBE	-	6.0×10^{-4}	-
$ \alpha_{\mu e} $	1.8×10^{-2}	1.4×10^{-2}	1.9×10^{-5}	5.4×10^{-4}
$ \alpha_{\tau e} $	6.1×10^{-2} NOMAD	2.2×10^{-2}	6.2×10^{-3}	1.5×10^{-3}
$ \alpha_{\tau\mu} $	9.1×10^{-3}	2.6×10^{-2}	6.9×10^{-3}	1.5×10^{-4}

Oscillations

EW+CLFV
precision
data

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Present Bounds

$$|\alpha_{\beta\beta}|^2 = \frac{1}{2} \sum_i |\theta_{\alpha i}|^2$$

Figure from Bolton, Deppisch, Bhupal Dev 1912.03058

Low Scale Non-Unitarity (DUNE ND)

③ SMEFT

Effective Operators
(New BSM states
integrated out)

3 SMEFT

- Consider SM as a low energy effective theory. New Physics effects are parametrized via non-renormalizable effective operators (built upon the SM field content and **respecting the SM gauge symmetry**) suppressed by the New Physics scale Λ :

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{SM}} + \overset{1/\Lambda}{\mathcal{L}_{d=5}} + \underset{1/\Lambda^2}{\mathcal{L}_{d=6}} + \dots$$

- Beyond $d=5$ (**Weinberg operator**) generating **neutrino masses**, the least suppressed New Physics effects would appear in **$d=6$ operators** usually normalized as

$$\mathcal{L}_{d=6} = \sum_i \frac{c_i}{v^2} \mathcal{O}_i$$

NSI from SMEFT

- After the electroweak symmetry breaking, some SMEFT operators generate NSI neutrino interactions that can be probed in neutrino oscillations. For instance

NSI from SMEFT

- After the electroweak symmetry breaking, some SMEFT operators generate NSI neutrino interactions that can be probed in neutrino oscillations. For instance

➔
EWSB

We need to identify *in which part of the SMEFT parameter space neutrino oscillations can significantly contribute!*

However, *strong bounds* from LEP and other experiments *on SMEFT induced NSI!*

NSI from SMEFT

- New physics effects at neutrino experiments can be parameterized by most general NSI Lagrangian: **neutral current (NC)** and **charged current (CC)** NSI

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{NC-NSI}} \supset -2\sqrt{2}G_F \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{f,X} (\bar{\nu}_\alpha \gamma_\mu P_L \nu_\beta) (\bar{f} \gamma^\mu P_X f)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{CC-NSI}} \supset -2\sqrt{2}G_F \left\{ \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{\mu e X} (\bar{\nu}_\alpha \gamma_\mu P_L \nu_\beta) (\bar{\mu} \gamma^\mu P_X e) + \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{ud X} (\bar{e}_\alpha \gamma_\mu P_L \nu_\beta) (\bar{u} \gamma^\mu P_X d) + \dots \right\}$$

NSI from SMEFT (LFC)

- New physics effects at neutrino experiments can be parameterized by most general NSI Lagrangian: **neutral current (NC)** and **charged current (CC)** NSI

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{NC-NSI}} \supset -2\sqrt{2}G_F \varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^{f,X} (\bar{\nu}_\alpha \gamma_\mu P_L \nu_\alpha) (\bar{f} \gamma^\mu P_X f)$$

Coloma, Fernandez-Martinez, JLP, Marcano, Naredo-Tuero, Urrea 2411.00090

- *Stringent constraints on **LFC CC-NSI beyond sensitivity of neutrino oscillation experiments.***

- *When the indirect dependence from the modification of neutrino fluxes and cross sections is properly accounted for, the **sensitivity to exclusively LFC CC-NSI is lost.***

Contribution of Neutrino Experiments to LFC SMEFT

Coloma, Fernandez-Martinez, JLP, Marcano, Naredo-Tuero, Urrea
2411.00090

Bresó-Pla, Falkowski,
González-Alonso, Monsálvez-Pozo
2301.07036

Contribution of Neutrino Experiments to LFC SMEFT

Operators	1σ interval	
	Non-Osc.	Non-Osc. + Osc. + CE ν NS
$[\hat{c}_{eq}]_{ee11}$	0.76 ± 1.80	0.07 ± 0.30
$[c_{lu}]_{\mu\mu11}$	0.110 ± 0.091	0.058 ± 0.076
$[c_{ld}]_{\mu\mu11}$	0.19 ± 0.27	0.11 ± 0.25
$[\hat{c}_{\ell q}^{(1)}]_{\tau\tau11}$	Unconstrained	0.07 ± 0.19
$[\hat{c}_{lu}]_{\tau\tau11}$	Unconstrained	-0.04 ± 0.54

Coloma, Fernandez-Martinez, JLP, Marcano, Naredo-Tuero, Urrea
2411.00090

Previously pointed out in Bresó-Pla, Falkowski, González-Alonso, Monsálvez-Pozo 2301.07036

$[\hat{c}_{eq}]_{ee11}$ $[\hat{c}_{lu}]_{ee11}$ $[\hat{c}_{ld}]_{ee11}$ $[c_{\ell q}^{(1)}]_{\mu\mu11}$ $[c_{lu}]_{\mu\mu11}$ $[c_{ld}]_{\mu\mu11}$ $[\hat{c}_{\ell q}^{(1)}]_{\tau\tau11}$ $[\hat{c}_{lu}]_{\tau\tau11}$

Conclusions

- Current constraints on NU from EW and CLFV precision data well beyond sensitivity of oscillation experiments.

Best chance: Future CLFV experiments and FCC-ee EW precision data.

- For kinematically accessible sterile neutrino the EW and CLFV bounds do not apply and NU-like effects generated in the averaged out regime. *Still stringent constraints from short baseline oscillation experiments and experiments strongly sensitive to matter effects.*

- Near detectors at future oscillation experiments are probably the best option to test robustness of standard 3 neutrino picture. *Keeping under control shape uncertainties is a key issue.*

- Neutrino experiments can probe new directions (operators) of SMEFT parameter space and improve over current global bounds.

Thank you!

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and the European Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR

Contribution to (LFV) SMEFT

SMEFT global bounds with u, d quarks

Contribution to (LFV) SMEFT

	up-quarks		down-quarks
$\mathcal{O}_{\alpha\beta L}^{uV}$	$(\bar{u}\gamma_\mu u)(\bar{e}_{L\alpha}\gamma^\mu e_{L\beta})$	$\mathcal{O}_{\alpha\beta L}^{dV}$	$(\bar{d}\gamma_\mu d)(\bar{e}_{L\alpha}\gamma^\mu e_{L\beta})$
$\mathcal{O}_{\alpha\beta L}^{uA}$	$(\bar{u}\gamma_\mu\gamma_5 u)(\bar{e}_{L\alpha}\gamma^\mu e_{L\beta})$	$\mathcal{O}_{\alpha\beta L}^{dA}$	$(\bar{d}\gamma_\mu\gamma_5 d)(\bar{e}_{L\alpha}\gamma^\mu e_{L\beta})$
$\mathcal{O}_{\alpha\beta R}^{uV}$	$(\bar{u}\gamma_\mu u)(\bar{e}_{R\alpha}\gamma^\mu e_{R\beta})$	$\mathcal{O}_{\alpha\beta R}^{dV}$	$(\bar{d}\gamma_\mu d)(\bar{e}_{R\alpha}\gamma^\mu e_{R\beta})$
$\mathcal{O}_{\alpha\beta R}^{uA}$	$(\bar{u}\gamma_\mu\gamma_5 u)(\bar{e}_{R\alpha}\gamma^\mu e_{R\beta})$	$\mathcal{O}_{\alpha\beta R}^{dA}$	$(\bar{d}\gamma_\mu\gamma_5 d)(\bar{e}_{R\alpha}\gamma^\mu e_{R\beta})$
$\mathcal{O}_{\alpha\beta R}^{uS}$	$(\bar{u}u)(\bar{e}_{L\alpha}e_{R\beta}) + \text{h.c.}$	$\mathcal{O}_{\alpha\beta R}^{dS}$	$(\bar{d}d)(\bar{e}_{L\alpha}e_{R\beta}) + \text{h.c.}$
$\mathcal{O}_{\alpha\beta R}^{uP}$	$(\bar{u}\gamma_5 u)(\bar{e}_{L\alpha}e_{R\beta}) + \text{h.c.}$	$\mathcal{O}_{\alpha\beta R}^{dP}$	$(\bar{d}\gamma_5 d)(\bar{e}_{L\alpha}e_{R\beta}) + \text{h.c.}$
$\mathcal{O}_{\alpha\beta R}^{uT}$	$(\bar{u}\sigma_{\mu\nu}u)(\bar{e}_{L\alpha}\sigma^{\mu\nu}e_{R\beta}) + \text{h.c.}$	$\mathcal{O}_{\alpha\beta R}^{dT}$	$(\bar{d}\sigma_{\mu\nu}d)(\bar{e}_{L\alpha}\sigma^{\mu\nu}e_{R\beta}) + \text{h.c.}$

$$c_{\alpha\beta L}^{uV} = -\frac{1}{2} \left[c_{lu} + c_{lq}^{(1)} - c_{lq}^{(3)} \right]_{\alpha\beta 11} + \left(1 - \frac{8}{3} s_w^2 \right) [\delta g_L^{Ze}]_{\alpha\beta}$$

$$c_{\alpha\beta L}^{uA} = -\frac{1}{2} \left[c_{lu} - c_{lq}^{(1)} + c_{lq}^{(3)} \right]_{\alpha\beta 11} - [\delta g_L^{Ze}]_{\alpha\beta},$$

$$c_{\alpha\beta R}^{uV} = -\frac{1}{2} [c_{eu} + c_{eq}]_{\alpha\beta 11} + \left(1 - \frac{8}{3} s_w^2 \right) [\delta g_R^{Ze}]_{\alpha\beta},$$

$$c_{\alpha\beta R}^{uA} = -\frac{1}{2} [c_{eu} - c_{eq}]_{\alpha\beta 11} - [\delta g_R^{Ze}]_{\alpha\beta},$$

$$c_{\alpha\beta L}^{dV} = -\frac{1}{2} \left[c_{ld} + c_{lq}^{(1)} + c_{lq}^{(3)} \right]_{\alpha\beta 11} - \left(1 - \frac{4}{3} s_w^2 \right) [\delta g_L^{Ze}]_{\alpha\beta}$$

$$c_{\alpha\beta L}^{dA} = -\frac{1}{2} \left[c_{ld} - c_{lq}^{(1)} - c_{lq}^{(3)} \right]_{\alpha\beta 11} + [\delta g_L^{Ze}]_{\alpha\beta},$$

$$c_{\alpha\beta R}^{dV} = -\frac{1}{2} [c_{ed} + c_{eq}]_{\alpha\beta 11} - \left(1 - \frac{4}{3} s_w^2 \right) [\delta g_R^{Ze}]_{\alpha\beta},$$

$$c_{\alpha\beta R}^{dA} = -\frac{1}{2} [c_{ed} - c_{eq}]_{\alpha\beta 11} + [\delta g_R^{Ze}]_{\alpha\beta},$$

$$c_{\alpha\beta R}^{uS} = c_{\alpha\beta R}^{uP} = \frac{1}{2} [c_{lequ}^{(1)}]_{\alpha\beta 11},$$

$$c_{\alpha\beta R}^{dS} = -c_{\alpha\beta R}^{dP} = -\frac{1}{2} [c_{ledq}]_{\alpha\beta 11},$$

$$c_{\alpha\beta R}^{uT} = \frac{1}{2} [c_{lequ}^{(3)}]_{\alpha\beta 11},$$

Mapping between NSI and SMEFT

CC-NSI assuming **LFV** (lepton flavour violation)

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{\mu e L} = -\frac{1}{2}[c_{ll}]_{\alpha\beta\mu e} + \delta_{\alpha\beta}[\delta g_L^{Ze}]_{\mu e} + \delta_{\mu\beta}[\delta g_L^{We}]_{e\alpha} + \delta_{e\alpha}[\delta g_L^{We}]_{\mu\beta},$$

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{\mu e R} = -\frac{1}{2}[c_{le}]_{\alpha\beta\mu e} + \delta_{\alpha\beta}[\delta g_R^{Ze}]_{\mu e},$$

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{udL} = -[c_{\ell q}^{(3)}]_{\alpha\beta 11} + [\delta g_L^{We}]_{\alpha\beta},$$

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{udR} = 0,$$

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{udS} = -\frac{1}{2} \left([c_{\ell equ}^{(1)}]_{\beta\alpha 11}^* + [c_{ledq}]_{\beta\alpha 11}^* \right),$$

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{udP} = -\frac{1}{2} \left([c_{ledq}]_{\beta\alpha 11}^* - [c_{\ell equ}^{(1)}]_{\beta\alpha 11}^* \right),$$

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{udT} = -\frac{1}{2}[c_{\ell equ}^{(3)}]_{\beta\alpha 11}^*.$$

Contribution to (LFV) SMEFT

$$\tilde{P}_{\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e}^{\text{KARMEN}} = \sum_{\alpha} p_{XY}^{\mu} \varepsilon_{\alpha e}^{\mu e X} \varepsilon_{\alpha e}^{\mu e Y} + d_{XY}^{\beta} \varepsilon_{e\mu}^{udX} \varepsilon_{e\mu}^{udY} + 2d_{XL}^{\beta} p_{YL}^{\mu} \varepsilon_{e\mu}^{udX} \varepsilon_{ee}^{\mu e Y} < 6.5 \cdot 10^{-4},$$

$$\tilde{P}_{\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e}^{\text{NOMAD}} = p_{XY}^{\pi} \varepsilon_{\mu e}^{udX} \varepsilon_{\mu e}^{udY} + d_{XY}^{ud} \varepsilon_{e\mu}^{udX} \varepsilon_{e\mu}^{udY} + 2d_{XL}^{ud} p_{YL}^{\pi} \varepsilon_{e\mu}^{udX} \varepsilon_{\mu e}^{udY} < 7.0 \cdot 10^{-4},$$

$$\text{KARMEN} \begin{cases} p_{LL}^{\mu} = 1, & p_{RR}^{\mu} = \frac{6m_{\mu} - 12E_{\nu}}{3m_{\mu} - 4E_{\nu}}, \\ d_{LL}^{\beta} = 1, & d_{SS}^{\beta} = \frac{g_S^2}{1 + 3g_A^2}, & d_{TT}^{\beta} = \frac{g_T^2}{1 + 3g_A^2}, \end{cases}$$

$$\text{NOMAD} \begin{cases} p_{LL}^{\pi} = 1, & p_{PL}^{\pi} = \frac{m_{\pi}^2}{m_{\mu}(m_u + m_d)}, & p_{PP}^{\pi} = \frac{m_{\pi}^4}{m_{\mu}^2(m_u + m_d)^2}, \\ d_{LL}^{ud} \simeq 0.91, & d_{SS}^{ud} = d_{PP}^{ud} \simeq 0.04, & d_{TT}^{ud} \simeq 0.59, \end{cases}$$

NC-NSI from SMEFT

NSI	95% C.L. bound	
	Osc. + CEνNS	Non-Osc. + Osc. + CEνNS
ε_{ee}^\oplus	(-0.58, 0.50)	(-0.75, 0.16)
$\varepsilon_{\mu\mu}^\oplus$	(-0.61, 0.47)	(-0.79, 0.11)
$\varepsilon_{\tau\tau}^\oplus$	(-0.62, 0.43)	(-0.80, 0.08)
$\varepsilon_{ee}^\oplus - \varepsilon_{\mu\mu}^\oplus$	(-0.14, 0.27)	(-0.14, 0.27)
$\varepsilon_{\tau\tau}^\oplus - \varepsilon_{\mu\mu}^\oplus$	(-0.014, 0.025)	(-0.014, 0.025)

Contribution to (LFC) SMEFT

$$\frac{d\sigma_{\alpha}^{\text{coh}}(E_R, E_{\nu})}{dE_R} = \frac{G_F^2}{2\pi} \sum_{\beta} |Q_{\alpha\beta}|^2 F^2(q^2) m_A \left(2 - \frac{m_A E_R}{E_{\nu}^2} \right),$$

$$Q_{\alpha\beta} = Z(g_p^V \delta_{\alpha\beta} + \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{p,V}) + N(g_n^V \delta_{\alpha\beta} + \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{n,V}),$$

$$\downarrow$$

$$2\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{u,V} + \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{d,V}$$

$$\downarrow$$

$$2\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{d,V} + \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{u,V}$$

Coherent

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{\oplus} = \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{e,V} + (2 + Y_n^{\oplus})\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{u,V} + (1 + 2Y_n^{\oplus})\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{d,V}$$

Matter Effects

$$\varepsilon^{\text{SNO}} \approx \sum_{\alpha} \varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^{u,A} - \varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^{d,A} \quad \text{SNO (NC)}$$

Mapping between NSI and SMEFT

NC-NSI assuming **LFC** (lepton flavour conservation)

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^{e,V} &= \delta_{e\alpha} \left(\delta g_L^{We} - \delta g_L^{W\mu} + \frac{1}{2} [c_{ll}]_{e\mu\mu e} \right) - (1 - 4s_w^2) \delta g_L^{Z\nu\alpha} + \delta g_L^{Ze} + \delta g_R^{Ze} \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \left([c_{ll}]_{ee\alpha\alpha} + [c_{le}]_{\alpha\alpha ee} \right),\end{aligned}$$

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^{u,V} = \delta g_L^{Zu} + \delta g_R^{Zu} + \left(1 - \frac{8}{3} s_w^2 \right) \delta g^{Z\nu\alpha} - \frac{1}{2} \left([c_{lq}^{(1)}]_{\alpha\alpha 11} + [c_{lq}^{(3)}]_{\alpha\alpha 11} + [c_{lu}]_{\alpha\alpha 11} \right)$$

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^{d,V} = \delta g_L^{Zd} + \delta g_R^{Zd} - \left(1 - \frac{4}{3} s_w^2 \right) \delta g^{Z\nu\alpha} - \frac{1}{2} \left([c_{lq}^{(1)}]_{\alpha\alpha 11} - [c_{lq}^{(3)}]_{\alpha\alpha 11} + [c_{ld}]_{\alpha\alpha 11} \right)$$

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^{u,A} = \delta g_L^{Zu} - \delta g_R^{Zu} + \delta g^{Z\nu\alpha} - \frac{1}{2} \left([c_{lq}^{(1)}]_{\alpha\alpha 11} + [c_{lq}^{(3)}]_{\alpha\alpha 11} - [c_{lu}]_{\alpha\alpha 11} \right),$$

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^{d,A} = \delta g_L^{Zd} - \delta g_R^{Zd} - \delta g^{Z\nu\alpha} - \frac{1}{2} \left([c_{lq}^{(1)}]_{\alpha\alpha 11} - [c_{lq}^{(3)}]_{\alpha\alpha 11} - [c_{ld}]_{\alpha\alpha 11} \right),$$

Contribution to (LFC) SMEFT

$$\varepsilon_{\tau\tau}^{\oplus} \longrightarrow [\hat{c}_{\ell q}^{(1)}]_{\tau\tau 11} = [c_{\ell q}^{(1)}]_{\tau\tau 11} + \frac{2 + Y_n^{\oplus}}{3(1 + Y_n^{\oplus})} [c_{lu}]_{\tau\tau 11} + \frac{1 + 2Y_n^{\oplus}}{3(1 + Y_n^{\oplus})} [c_{ld}]_{\tau\tau 11},$$

$$\text{SNO} \longrightarrow [\hat{c}_{lu}]_{\tau\tau 11} = [c_{lu}]_{\tau\tau 11} - [c_{ld}]_{\tau\tau 11}.$$

Role of shape uncertainty

- Sensitivity driven by spectral information.
- Marginal impact of global normalization error.

General Parameterizations

- Hermitian parameterization

$$N = (I - \eta) U'$$

Deviation from unitarity

$$\eta = \begin{pmatrix} \eta_{ee} & \eta_{e\mu} & \eta_{e\tau} \\ \eta_{e\mu}^* & \eta_{\mu\mu} & \eta_{\mu\tau} \\ \eta_{e\tau}^* & \eta_{\mu\tau}^* & \eta_{\tau\tau} \end{pmatrix} = \frac{\Theta\Theta^\dagger}{2}$$

Unitarity matrix
(standard unitary PMNS
matrix
up to small corrections)

Broncano, Gavela, Jenkins 2003

Fernandez-Martinez, Gavela, JLP, Yasuda 2007

Mapping

$$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{ee} & 0 & 0 \\ \alpha_{\mu e} & \alpha_{\mu\mu} & 0 \\ \alpha_{\tau e} & \alpha_{\tau\mu} & \alpha_{\tau\tau} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \eta_{ee} & 0 & 0 \\ 2\eta_{e\mu}^* & \eta_{\mu\mu} & 0 \\ 2\eta_{e\tau}^* & 2\eta_{\mu\tau}^* & \eta_{\tau\tau} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\theta_{12} - \theta'_{12} = \frac{\operatorname{Re}(s_{23}\eta_{e\tau} - c_{23}\eta_{e\mu})}{c_{13}},$$

$$\theta_{13} - \theta'_{13} = \operatorname{Re}(-s_{23}e^{i\delta_{\text{CP}}}\eta_{e\mu} - c_{23}e^{i\delta_{\text{CP}}}\eta_{e\tau}), \quad U = U' + O(\eta)$$

$$\theta_{23} - \theta'_{23} = -\operatorname{Re}(\eta_{\mu\tau}) + \tan\theta_{13} \operatorname{Re}(c_{23}e^{i\delta_{\text{CP}}}\eta_{e\mu} - s_{23}e^{i\delta_{\text{CP}}}\eta_{e\tau}),$$

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_{\text{CP}} - \delta'_{\text{CP}} &= \frac{\cos 2\theta_{12}}{s_{12}c_{12}c_{13}} \operatorname{Im}(s_{23}\eta_{e\tau} - c_{23}\eta_{e\mu}) + \frac{1}{s_{13}c_{13}} \operatorname{Im}(s_{23}e^{i\delta_{\text{CP}}}\eta_{e\mu} + c_{23}e^{i\delta_{\text{CP}}}\eta_{e\tau}) \\ &\quad - \frac{\tan\theta_{13}}{s_{23}c_{23}} \operatorname{Im}\left(c_{23}^3e^{i\delta_{\text{CP}}}\eta_{e\mu} + s_{23}^3e^{i\delta_{\text{CP}}}\eta_{e\tau} + \frac{\eta_{\mu\tau}}{\tan\theta_{13}}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Event Rate and Normalization

$$R_{\alpha}^{\text{CC},\beta}(L) = \frac{N_S N_T}{32\pi L^2 E_S m_T E_{\nu}} \sum_{k,l} e^{-i \frac{\Delta m_{kl}^2 L}{2E_{\nu}}} \int d\Pi_{P'} \mathcal{M}_{\alpha k}^P \overline{\mathcal{M}}_{\alpha l}^P \int d\Pi_D \mathcal{M}_{\beta k}^D \overline{\mathcal{M}}_{\beta l}^D$$

QFT

$$R_{\alpha}^{\text{CC},\beta}(L) = N_T \Phi_{\alpha} P_{\alpha\beta}(L) \frac{d\sigma_{\beta}}{dE_{\nu}}$$

$$P_{\alpha\beta}(L) = \frac{R_{\alpha}^{\text{CC},\beta}(L)}{N_T \Phi_{\alpha}^{\text{est}} \frac{d\sigma_{\beta}^{\text{est}}}{dE_{\nu}}}$$

Experiments

Why is there confusion in literature?

- Potentially interesting alternative: *to avoid parameterizing deviations from unitarity*
Parke, Ross-Lonergan, 1508.05095; Ellis, Kelly, Li, 2004.13719; Ellis, Kelly, Li, 2008.01088
- Unitarity triangles in the quark sector are successful unitarity test: independent measurements of the individual V_{ab}^{CKM} compared to test unitarity conditions.
- This is **not efficient in the lepton sector** because, contrary to the quark sector, only charged leptons are detected and thus **a direct measurement of $N_{\alpha i}$ is not directly possible!**
- *Avoiding using a convenient parameterization might lead to wrong conclusions.*
- Zero distance and matter effects are directly sensitive to α . **Our current knowledge of the lepton mixing matrix is that it is close to unitary with higher accuracy than the uncertainty we have in its individual entries.**

$$(NN^\dagger)_{\beta\gamma} \approx \delta_{\beta\gamma} - \alpha_{\beta\gamma} - \alpha_{\gamma\beta}^*$$

3+1 Sterile Neutrinos: $P_{\mu\mu} + P_{\mu e} + P_{ee}$

3+1 Sterile Neutrinos:

P_{ee}

Constraints from neutrino mass mechanism

- Generation of light neutrino masses imposes **constraints on HNL mixing and thus on NU parameters**

$$m_\nu = \frac{v^2}{2} Y^T M^{-1} Y = \boxed{\theta M \theta^T} = \boxed{U m U^T}$$

↓ ↓

HNL sector Light-active neutrino sector

Minimal model ($n_R=2$): Flavor structure

Blennow, Fernandez-Martinez, Hernandez-Garcia,
 JLP, Marcano, Naredo-Tuero 2306.01040
 Abdullahi et al 2203.08039
 Drewes, Klaric, JLP 2207.02742
 Caputo, Hernandez, JLP, Salvado, 1704.08721

Minimal model ($n_R=2$): Flavor structure

DUNE forecast assuming $\delta = -\pi/2$

Blennow, Fernandez-Martinez, Hernandez-Garcia,
 JLP, Marcano, Naredo-Tuero 2306.01040
 Abdullahi et al 2203.08039
 Drewes, Klaric, JLP 2207.02742
 Caputo, Hernandez, JLP, Salvado, 1704.08721

PMNS CP-phases from HNLs searches

$N_R = 2$

- **Potential determination of the PMNS Majorana phase!**

Hernandez, Kekic, JLP, Racker, Salvado 1606.06719
Caputo, Hernandez, Kekic, JLP, Salvado 1611.05000

Approximated LNC

$$M_\nu = \begin{pmatrix} \overline{\nu^c} & \overline{N}_1 & \overline{N}_2 & L \\ 1 & -1 & 1 & \\ 0 & Y_1^T v/\sqrt{2} & \epsilon Y_2^T v/\sqrt{2} & 1 \\ Y_1 v/\sqrt{2} & \mu' & \Lambda & -1 \\ \epsilon Y_2 v/\sqrt{2} & \Lambda & \mu & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{matrix} \nu \\ N_1^c \\ N_2^c \end{matrix}$$

- Light nu masses suppressed with LNV parameters

$$m_\nu = \mu \frac{v^2}{2\Lambda^2} Y_1^T Y_1 + \frac{v^2}{2\Lambda} \epsilon Y_2^T Y_1 + \frac{v^2}{2\Lambda} Y_1^T \epsilon Y_2$$

- Quasi-Dirac heavy neutrinos with large mixings:

$$M_2 \approx M_1 \approx \Lambda \quad \Delta M \approx \mu' + \mu \quad \theta \sim Y_1 v/\Lambda$$